

Infrastructural Railway Barriers and Spatial Segregation in Sofia. From Historical Roots Towards Possible Entanglements

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Abstract

The history reveals that in the pre-industrial years Sofia plain regional urban metabolism was almost fully circular. This rapid urbanisation processes at the end of 19th and throughout the 20th century have unfolded large industrial and extraction activity and concentrated around one third of the country's population in the capital city. With the industrialisation and the development of the railways its connection on international level the urban metabolism then turned into linear. The destruction of environmental qualities have affected mostly the poorer neighbourhoods and residents. Infrastructures began to divide the city but as well have implications on the social fabric. Sofia is segregated by its main infrastructural division line – the railway corridor connecting Belgrade and Istanbul – on a poorer northern part and richer southern part. The case of Hristo Botev neighbourhood shows an extreme segregation of a residential zone from its urban environment and welfare infrastructure via total enclosure by linear and spatial infrastructural barriers. The activist mobilisation of the Gradoscope collective, described in the paper, creates a platform for an open-ended process for an expert and civil conversation about the future urban development of the railway corridor as well as for spatial and climate justice.

Keywords

Infrastructure,
spatial segregation,
urban history, urban
inequality, urban
regeneration

Introduction

Urbanised territories are characterised by infrastructural barriers. Large infrastructure networks connect large industrial users with transport, water or electricity supply, while physically separating adjacent residential neighbourhoods usually populated by poorer residents from other parts of the city (Graham and Marvin, 2001). Conversely, infrastructure could be seen as the one large-scale project investment directed by public authorities, which allows them to pursue both progressive policies and the formation of new quality public and landscape spaces (Shannon & Smets, 2010). The social fabric of many mid-sized or large cities

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in Europe or North America is significantly affected by the departure of industry, leading to a pronounced and deepening divide between affluent and impoverished neighbourhoods (Secchi, 2015). Recent trends in infrastructure design increasingly target these issues, aiming to incorporate infrastructure into integrated projects. 'Once married with architecture, mobility, and landscape, infrastructure can more meaningfully integrate territories, reduce marginalisation and segregation, and stimulate new forms of interaction. It can then truly become "landscape."' (Shannon & Smets, 2010, pg.9). This partly explains the growing movement to shift perspectives and view infrastructure barriers as 'adaptive infrastructures.' Infrastructure networks should be seen not only as fulfilling a strictly functional and technical role but also as an integral part of the urban fabric, inscribed within the landscape's ecological characteristics and enhancing social connectivity.

The case of Sofia is an apt case study of how modern infrastructure networks have reinforced particular spatial and social inequalities. In Bulgaria railways began operating in 1866 with the construction of the first Ruse-Varna line, followed by the line connecting Belgrade and Istanbul, which passed through the new capital, Sofia. The development of railway infrastructure symbolised industrial progress and represented a clear statement of Bulgaria's emergence as a new progressive European country in the Balkans at the end of the 19th century.

Throughout its development, Bulgaria's railway network was closely tied to the country's industrialisation and modernisation. However, in the 1980s, the state radically reduced investment in the railways, leading to a gradual decline in both the quantity and quality of this transport service¹. This left once-busy tracks and large industrial sites as empty voids in the urban fabric. Railway infrastructure often acts as a barrier and physical divider between residential neighbourhoods (Athens Charter, 1933:58). In this sense, the fact that the tracks and their adjacent land remain state-owned positions railway companies as potentially significant players in the innovative arena of sustainable urban development and progressive urban policies.

This text focuses on the case of Sofia where the main railway line divides the city into northern and southern parts. Our primary research question is: Which are the main infrastructural barriers and how do they affect the welfare of residents in the bordering neighbourhoods? We also explore two sub-questions: (1) How has the history of industrialisation of the Sofia plain contributed to the contemporary infrastructural barriers in the urban fabric and (2) How can negotiation between stakeholders address the problems of spatial segregation and urban social inequalities.

¹ The highest peak in railway transport use in Bulgaria was in 1985 - the Bulgarian national railways transported around 86,000 mln ton-kilometres of materials and 108 mln passengers. For comparison the numbers for 2024 are respectively – 4,555 mln ton-kilometres of materials and 21,8 mln passengers. (National Statistical Institute).

In order to answer these questions we reviewed the literature on the environmental, infrastructural, and railway development of Sofia plain. We conducted site visits, took photographs, and performed extensive mapping exercises to summarise our own spatial findings, including landscape features, green and blue structures, and transport infrastructure. Additionally, we summarise the results series of rountables that we organised, which engaged citizens and experts alike.

The first part of the article tells the history of industrialisation, railway construction, and the formation of the contemporary urban fabric of the Sofia plain, with a particular focus on the railway infrastructure that splits the city into southern and northern parts. The second part examines Sofia's contemporary urban fabric through the lens of infrastructural barriers and spatial segregation, arguing that the city's current social divisions at the neighbourhood level have been partly the product of the long-time presence of large scale infrastructural objects that are difficult to traverse. The third part describes an episode of activist work by the Gradoscope collective in Sofia of which the authors are members. Gradoscope's work represents an effort to initiate an expert and public conversation about our findings with the institutions involved in further developing Sofia's railway infrastructures, namely the National Railway Infrastructure Company, Sofia Municipality, as well as expert and activist groups.

Railways, Industrialisation, and the Formation of the Contemporary Urban Fabric of Sofia

Transportation as a "condition for modern life"

The industrialisation, globalisation, and modern developments of the 19th and 20th centuries made transportation a 'condition for modern life' (Shannon & Smets, 2010). The infrastructural networks developed, particularly railways, constituted the technical means necessary for the industrial era to provide global access to resources, and thus turning circular regional metabolisms² into linear ones. Today, these redundant infrastructures continue to structure entire regions – both hinterland and urban territories. Regardless of a region's specific geographical advantages, the modern landscape is the product of these historical transformations (Cronnon, 1991).

In today's post-growth era, the spatial fabric of European cities remains marked by the departure of industry, with post-infrastructural heritage sites becoming urban voids. This exacerbates the divide between socially distinct groups and neighbourhoods. The first part of

² We use the term regional (or territorial) metabolism to describe the material resource management of a given urbanised region or a larger territory, thus replacing the concept of sustainable development. Regional metabolism refers to the balance of import, use, export, and disposal of air, water, biomass, materials, energy, and other resources (Baccini, 1996).

this paper examines the evolving relations between landscape, resources, infrastructures, and built environment. We investigate the ways in which industrialisation, railway network development, and urban growth transformed the regional metabolism of the Sofia plain and disturbed its longstanding ecosystemic balance. Already during the 1970s and 1980s various Bulgarian geographers signaled the profound effects that infrastructures and industrialization had on the conditions of life in the plain: ‘The environmental pollution in Sofia valley evokes adverse social, economic and ecological consequences’ (Georgiev, Blagoeva, Kandev, Konteva, 1980, p. 129). Who bears the cost today and what are the segregating consequences from it?

The use of technics and the man-made landscape

In his book *Technics and Civilization* (1934) Lewis Mumford identifies several stages of human history in relation to the use of technics and mechanical development: the *eotechnic* (the middle ages), *paleotechnic* (Industrial Revolution), and *neotechnic* epochs (modern day). The different implementation of mechanics and spatial connectivity dramatically altered ways of life, and as a consequence, metabolic relations and resource use. ‘Wherever the rails went, they brought sudden sweeping change to the landscapes and communities through which they passed (..) They do wonders- they work miracles’ (Cronnon, 1991, p 72).

The man-made landscape formed during the paleo- and neotechnic periods (Mumford: 1934) is the youngest and most dynamic morphological structural element. In its genesis it can be divided into the following categories: industrial and manufacturing, mining, agro-technical, hydro-technical, transport, archaeological and military (M. Georgiev, 1979). Each one of those human-made landscape modifications creates a spatial barrier due to its size and morphological shape. In 1980 Sofia basin concentrated 14% of electrical energy production, 80% of the iron and steel industry, more than 17% of the manufacturing sector, over 16% of the chemical industry, and other smaller segments of Bulgarian industrial and production activity. (Georgiev et al, 1980) In order to outline the regions under the heaviest pressure of human activities, and trace out the nature and intensity of the morpho-sculptural processes in the Sofia valley were consulted several geographical, hydrological and geological studies dating from the period 1979-2022.

Formation of the man-made landscape in the Sofia plain

The largest amongst the valleys extended between the Balkan Range mountains is the Sofia valley, covering a total area of around 1050 sq km. The long axis of the basin runs north-west to south-east for approximately 80 km, while the width of the valley varies between 20 and 30 km. The first ancient settlements in the Sofia plain emerged approximately 8000 years ago on the banks of the river Iskar. The city of Serdika developed as an important Roman polis

at the crossroads between Europe and Asia, on the road from Rome to Constantinople. The geographical factors that enhanced its development were its strategic location in the watershed alongside a fertile lower terrace of the plain suitable for agriculture, multiple natural thermal water springs, and its surrounding forests. The plain of Sofia was providing sufficient supplies in terms of food and resources (water, metals, wood) to its inhabitants, while creating a balanced equilibrium with the surrounding natural ecosystem. The pre-modernistic periods of the city's history are characterized by rather stable geographical conditions, rich natural ecosystems, consistent resource/metabolic flows and social/market relations, and self-regenerative, cyclic territorial metabolism. (*Figure 1*)

*Figure 1 - Sofia plain:
Neolit period (7000 BC) to 1878*

Figure 2 - Sofia plain: 1878 - 1944

*Figure 3 - Sofia plain:
1944 - Present*

With the foundation of the Third Bulgarian Kingdom in 1878, the process of industrialization commenced, altering the relationship between the city and the plain. (*Figure 2*) Historically inhabited by an agrarian society, industrial manufacturing was introduced in Bulgaria at the very end of the nineteenth century, after liberation from the Ottoman Empire, and focused mainly on the processing of agricultural produce from the region. During that initial stage, the small-scale factories were located on the outskirts of the city of Sofia, close to

the productive hinterland. However, during that period there was a lack of fundamental structural transformation³, and the less productive, labor-intensive, low-technology industries like food processing and textile fabrication dominated the sector. (Kopsidis, Ivanov, 2017). Rapid industrialization only took place after the Second World War.

In the period between 1878 and 1945, the so-called railway junction of Sofia was gradually formed on the line Paris – Istanbul (Orient Express). It consists of one main railway line (Belgrade – Istanbul) that runs through the five main stations of the city – Central, Stochna, Poduyane, Volyak and Iskar, followed by a second one north – west crossing it perpendicularly, and two bypass lines (*Figure 4*). Factories that emerged alongside them primarily focused on food and beverage manufacturing, processing the agricultural production of the Sofia plain. They had a strategic location between the city and the productive hinterland, alongside the railway tracks for efficient transportation.

In the end of the 19th and beginning of 20th century Sofia's population grew rapidly from 25.000 people to 450.000 people, due to several immigration waves. This caused major disruptions with housing and clean water provision. The Ottoman city was demolished and a new European capital was built, following the modernistic trends of the period.

Figure 4 - The development of the railway network in Sofia

³ The industrialization process is characterized by societal structural changes and reorganization. (Kopsidis, Ivanov: 2017) New societal groups are created: agrarian villagers move to the city and become urban workers. Those societal shifts lead to rapid urbanization and new spatial territorial organization.

During the Socialist era (1944-1989), the former Soviet Union dominated the country both politically and economically. More than any other nation in the region, Bulgaria's economy was patterned closely after the Soviet's, with a massive heavy-industrial sector, huge agro-industrial complexes, and ever-increasing urban concentrations and depopulation of the countryside (McIntyre 1988). During the Soviet period, Bulgaria was the eighth most industrialized country in the world (Pascaleva et al. 1998), but also among the least efficient and most polluting economies in the world (Solomon and Ahuja 1991; Paskaleva 1998).

The dynamic urbanization and industrialization during the Socialist period generated extensive transport, industrial, mining and agriculture activity. The densely developed railway network accelerated the industrial activities of excavation, mining and manufacturing, which in turn led to heavy pollution, degradation of the natural ecosystems, and spatial and social segregation throughout the Sofia Plain. However, the development of giant extraction and manufacturing sites did not necessarily correspond to the country's deposits of natural resources. Instead, the pursuit of production for ideological reasons represents the lack of environmental consideration in the Soviet development strategies (Paskaleva et al. 1998).

Nearly two thirds of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) during the socialist period came from heavy industry (World Bank, 1990). However, Bulgaria imported most of the raw materials, including fuels and ferrous metals from the Soviet Union (McIntyre 1988). Railways became fundamental—from the ports on the Black Sea for the import of the raw materials and the export of the semi-finished goods. Industrial and production zones surrounded the nation's cities and sustained an artificially created proletarian social group. Large amounts of raw materials and fuels were imported from the USSR. To pay for them, Sofia increased its exports of machinery, processed food, and manufactured consumer goods. Between 1955–7 and 1981–3, the share of machinery in major exports increased from 8.2 to 53.8%. (Kospidis, Ivanov 2017, 103)

Since 1989, as a consequence of the over industrialization, Bulgaria has experienced the greatest level of labor-shedding of any reforming Central East Europe¹ country. By 2019 it was deemed the fastest shrinking nation in the world (Hruby, 2019).

Characteristics of the man-made landscape in the Sofia plain

The population in Sofia plain rose from 450.000 people in the 1950s to nearly 2.000.000 today (*Figure 3*). The same flatness of the plain that 8000 years ago facilitated the settlement of the first residents and their agricultural activity, in recent history was a prerequisite for the construction of a railroad network three times denser than in the rest of the country, and the development of some of the largest industrial sites and extraction mines in Bulgaria. The bottom of the valley is characterised with predominantly architectural relief, due to the large concentration of settlements, factories, roads, railway lines and other major elements of this

type of relief. The belt between the mountain and the basin is mainly occupied by technogenic activity – quarries, mines, bulks, due to the very active excavation industry.

The highest levels of technogenic stress⁴ occur primarily in the northern, eastern, and southwestern regions of the Sofia basin (Georgiev 1979, Vlaskov, Simeonov 1992). These areas are characterised by extensive cut-and-fill landforms resulting from extraction, ore mining, and manufacturing industries. This type of landscape within the basin covers approximately 30 sq km. In contrast, man-made landscape forms associated with the building industry, railway and road construction, agriculture, and water supply, occupy a much larger area, exceeding 260 sq km (Vlaskov and Simeonov, 1992).

The mining landscape is linked to mineral resource extraction. The agro-technical one includes features such as anti-erosion terraces and drainage canals. Meanwhile, the hydrotechnical relief comprises dams, supply and drainage canals, as well as underground infrastructure, such as pipes for water supply and canalization. This category also encompasses the channelling and correction of river beds in both urban and rural areas. The dense transportation landscape in the plain includes a dense network of asphalted motorways and railways (M. Georgiev, 1979). The formation of these man-made landscapes, driven by social, economic, and ideological reasons, has significantly altered the natural metabolism and long-lived ecological balance of the Sofia plain over time. At present day, they represent spatial barriers segregating certain neighbourhoods and residents.

The effects on the natural ecosystems

In the late 1980s, the landscape of the Sofia valley had pronounced human intervention in its natural ecosystems, topography and landscape (Krumova, et al. 2000), and evoked adverse social, economic and ecological consequences (Georgiev et al. 1980, pg 129). The secondary landscape ruptures referred to the air, soil and water pollution.

<i>The effects on the natural ecosystems</i>				
<i>Pollution to</i>	<i>Typology</i>	<i>Due to</i>	<i>Where</i>	<i>Levels</i>
<i>Water</i>	industrial waste water discharges	phenols, petroleum products	most significant North and East part of the Sofia plain - Iskar, Lesnovska	in 1980 the levels were reaching 10-50 times over the accepted concentration levels
	domestic waste water discharges		Most significant in the city of Sofia	
<i>Air</i>	dust particles	fuels used in industry	in the Sofia plain: originating predominantly North and East areas, but distributing including over the capital	dust particles passing the accepted norms of maximum concentration 1 to 12 times
<i>Soil</i>	chemical pollution in the soils	chemical fertilizers		
	discharges of heavy metals in the form of dust	By products of the mining and the manufacturing activities - heavy metals - zinc, lead copper	highest around Novi Iskar and Kremikovtsi	varying between 100 to 600 mg/kg

Figure 5 - Chart, produced by the author, based on Georgiev (1980), Krumova (2000), Vlaskov (1992).

⁴ Technogenic stress here refers to the transformation of the environment and natural landscapes caused by industrial and technological processes during urbanisation, resource extraction and other human activity.

The industrial activity leads to the extinction of important agricultural lands and fertile soils in the areas of mining and construction sites. The River Iskar was highly polluted and declared unsuitable for agricultural, residential or recreational uses. (Georgiev, 1980) The constant pollution of surface waters was compounded by the worsened state of the underground waters, soils and the significant degradation of the natural complex. The geographical configuration of the Sofia plain by five distinct mountain ranges, creates limited air movement within the valley and conducive conditions for air pollution. In 1980, an average of 48% of the days throughout the year exceeded established air quality norms (Georgiev, 1980). The natural vegetation and habitat were highly transformed and largely extinct. (Georgiev, 1980; Vlaskov, Simeonov 1992; Krumova, Belov 2000). Many vegetation and animal species were completely extinct or declined significantly in numbers (particularly the vertebrate animals) (Vlaskov, Simeonov 1992).

A 2020 study commissioned by the Sofia Municipality (Naidenov and Pencheva, 2021) revealed that approximately 50% of the soils in the Sofia region are potentially polluted. This area encompasses agricultural lands, natural parks, protected areas, Natura 2000 sites, and extends to underground waters and the atmosphere.

The reasons for the spatial segregation, caused by the infrastructural development and the industrial activity, could be found in studies about the living conditions in the plain, dating from 1975. Following several analyses over the health of the population and the frequency of respiratory diseases in young people (until 15 years old), prof. M. Georgiev concluded that a more “healthy environment” was offered on the south part of Sofia, on the border of the slopes of the mountain Vitosha. Worse conditions, as higher air and water pollution, were present in the plain itself, so the northern (“poorer”) neighbourhoods of the capital.

Redundant infrastructures as a backbone for the post-growth landscape

After 1989, the state reduced investment in rail transport, and the quantity and quality of transport declined gradually. Additionally, some of the largest industrial sites closed due to privatisation, pollution and departure of the manufacturing activity from Bulgaria. The tonnage handled by the city's distributing cargo stations gradually diminished, on average handling 3-5 times less. The stations and much of the dense railway network once serving the industrial sites are slowly losing their past activity and are now huge-scale partially deserted sites, of around 500 ha in the city of Sofia. The problem of the re-cultivation of the post-industrial sites and infrastructures faces the same challenges on the scale of the plain as well in the city – abandonment, water, soil and air pollution, spatial barriers, extinction of vegetal and animal species, resource scarcity.

The “birth, life and death” of industrialization and infrastructure networks have severely interrupted the natural ecosystems (Bouw 2022: 103), which sustained the regional metabolisms through the history of human civilization. The short time-frame (only 30 years) and the inappropriate scale of industrialization (not depending on resource availability nor economic profitability, but on ideological and political reasons), leave today abandoned and decaying post-industrial overinfrastructured sites and infrastructures. Nature (and society at large) are in post-industrial condition. A question as to how infrastructure networks and sites can be re-envisioned as spatial structures to become a backbone of the post-growth ecological metabolism emerges. A new paradigm of urbanization unlocks the post-extraction/ industrial/ infrastructural landscape for experiment and dialogue within the context of Sofia plain.

Figure 6 - Mapping of landscape elements and transport infrastructure of the Sofia plain in the present.

Infrastructural Barriers and Community Severance

The politics of transport axis vs the lively urban environment

The analysis of Sofia’s history gives a solid base for a close look at the spatial segregation of the residential neighbourhoods caused by the development of modern infrastructure

throughout the 20th century. The construction of large stone and concrete riverbeds, the development of transnational railways, the construction of the Sofia airport, the late developments of large 4-6 lane urban motorways have erected infrastructural barriers within the urban landscape. The spatial segregation described here is not a process of simply unequal redistribution of certain social groups upon the urban territory. On the contrary, these barriers lead to unequal access to essential urban amenities like social infrastructure, transport, and green spaces.

This article draws on the substantive literature on the long-term implications of linear infrastructural elements on the quality of life in residential neighbourhoods. The notion of ‘community severance’, or the ‘barrier effect,’ is informed by a broader critique of modernist urban planning, represented among others by CIAM,⁵ which prioritised functional zoning and high-speed car traffic at the expense of community cohesion and environmental quality (Anciaes, 2016; Piekut, 2021). Many Western cities have followed this model of development. The well-known critiques of modernist urban planning – the texts of Jane Jacobs, Jan Gehl, the members of New Urbanism and TEAM 10 – laid the groundwork for a wave of theoretical, analytical, and practical work demonstrating the enormous destruction of natural environment, urban communities, lively urban fabric in favour of large infrastructural projects creating unhealthy environments dependant on fossil fuel energy.

Globally, there has been a shift towards more sustainable urban designs, emphasising pedestrianisation and public transport, as seen in the renovation of public spaces and the introduction of sustainable mobility policies in cities like Barcelona, Copenhagen, Amsterdam, London, Brussels, Paris, Ljubljana, Berlin, and New York City. A substantial political, expert, and financial effort has been mobilised towards creating pedestrian and bicycle infrastructure that would support a widely-used public transport network and provide means of transportation alternative to the ubiquitous reliance on automobiles.

The work of Adam Paul Susaneck, the founder of the Segregation by Design project, is an example of an initiative drawing on contemporary critiques of the modernist urban transport policies. Susaneck narrates the history of the Federal Urban Renewal Program and the construction of urban motorways and their impact on neighbourhoods of colour in US cities. Looking at dozens of highway projects in urban areas, Susaneck demonstrates how heavy road infrastructure has been used to systematically destroy and ‘enclose’ red-lined residential areas predominantly inhabited by people of colour (Susaneck, 2023).

Infrastructure cuts through the urban tissue of Sofia

⁵ Congrès international d'architecture moderne (CIAM) refers to a series of international events throughout Europe between 1928-59 that laid out some of the most influential urban planning, landscape and design principles of the time.

Historical studies have highlighted the fact that **railway infrastructure** proved the main dividing line in Sofia. In the past, the Belgrade-Istanbul railway line lay outside the compact urban structure, but nowadays it is an integral part of the city, dividing it into a bigger, largely residential, southern part and a smaller industrial, but also residential, northern part. This railway infrastructure remains a backbone of the country's transport system, positioning Sofia on an important axis between Europe and Asia. The railway axis connects several stations – passenger, freight and railway yards – and continues to be included in future development plans of the National Railway Infrastructure Company (NRIC). As part of a 2015 the company is renovating existing lines, adding new passenger stops for a RER system to integrate train services with Sofia's urban transport system. Nevertheless, some of the railway stations near the city centre, most notably the old freight station (Stochna gara) and the biggest railway yard (Poduyane Razpredelitelna station) have remained unused in recent decades as freight services in both the country and city have gradually declined (GSP Sofia, 2009).

The **rivers** flowing through Sofia are relatively small in debit but can swell significantly during torrential rains occurring multiple times a year. Prevention of heavy flooding in surrounding neighbourhoods necessitated the construction of stone and concrete river beds in the course of the 20th century. These structures, ranging from 15 to 25 metres in width and 8 to 10 metres in depth, serve as physical barriers that are seldom crossed by bridges. The rivers are still part of the city's sewage system, with main sewage collectors running along their beds . In case of sewage overflow, untreated water spills are spilling into the rivers, leaving behind sewage debris and a noticeable odour along the city rivers.

Urban motorways represent a third linear object cutting across residential neighbourhoods and gradually becoming an obstacle to pedestrian and bicycle movement within the city. While railways and river beds have very concrete monofunctional purposes, that is not the case with urban boulevards. The latter are intended to invite public use and facilitate informal social interactions among city dwellers (Gehl, 1971; Gehl, 2010). Nevertheless, the motorways in Sofia, constructed or refurbished in the last decade, have not been designed as spaces for public life, but rather as corridors for transport. Consequently, these motorways fail to meet their broader potential as multifunctional, inclusive public spaces. They have been primarily designed by transport engineers without considering the urban functions that boulevards could potentially fulfil.

The following mapping exercise (*Figure 7*) synthesises the existing infrastructural barriers and their overall spatial distribution across the city. This text zooms in on linear and infrastructural barriers and does not examine barrier effects that may result from larger

industrial zones, gated private residential or office developments, gated parks, etc. Their impact needs to be mapped in future analysis.

Figure 7 - Infrastructural barriers in Sofia – railways (red), urban motorways and the airport (yellow), river beds (purple)

Recent space syntax analysis⁶ reveals a marked pedestrian disconnectedness in areas north of Sofia's main railway line (Karamitov & Petrova-Antonova, 2022). The territories including and south from the city centre, on the other hand, seem to be integrated quite well. Space syntax analysis measures the visual connectedness of open spaces in the city structure and their potential for pedestrian movement, without taking into account the quality of urban spaces and their walkability or porosity for pedestrian movement.

⁶ "Space syntax is a theory of space and a set of analytical, quantitative and descriptive tools for analysing the layout of space in buildings and cities." <https://www.spacesyntax.online/term/space-syntax/>
Space syntax analysis gives us the possibility to measure the level of connectedness, orientation and accessibility of the urbanised region of Sofia.

Figure 8 - Spatial Syntax Integration Analysis without Search radius. Source: Karamitov & Petrova-Antonova (2022)

Social inequalities follow the pattern

The spatial divide between the south and the north side of the railway barrier aligns with socioeconomic inequalities. Sofia municipality data indicates that the residents of northern neighbourhoods earn ca. 10% less than the city average; residents in the south-western part of the city earn 10% to 20% above the city average, while city centre residents earn 20% more than the average (Figure 9).⁷ This income disparity between Sofia's well-off southern and poor northern areas is accentuated by the railway barrier.

⁷ Data about the residents and social infrastructure of Sofia have been gathered, systematised and published in open source formats in the period 2017-2022 by the municipal urban planning organisation Sofiaplan on <https://sofiaplan.bg/>.

Figure 9 - Average monthly income for individuals for 2017 as a percentage above/ under the average for the Sofia Municipality.

Source: Sofiaplan (<https://sofiaplan.bg/>)

Further data supports this hypothesis, showing a higher share of residents receiving social aid by the city in the northwestern areas (*Figure 10*). A greater concentration of people experiencing financial difficulties is observed in the northern and the north-western part of the city, further substantiating the conjecture about income disparity between the northern and southern regions.

Figure 10 - Concentration (in %) of residents, beneficiaries of social financial help from the Sofia Municipality.

Source: Sofiaplan (<https://sofiaplan.bg/>)

The analysis illustrates the concentration of cultural infrastructure in the city centre and its south-eastern periphery (*Figure 11*). The city centre houses most libraries, museums, theatres, galleries, cinemas and other cultural centres while the northern part is left with close to none. The cultural concentration gradually diminishes toward the southern and south-eastern neighbourhoods.

Figure 11 - Concentration of cultural infrastructure places

Source: Sofiaplan (<https://sofiaplan.bg/>)

Another indicator that we examined is the distribution of urban parks (both existing and planned) and their accessibility for residents without pedestrian access to any urban park (Figure 12). The map shows a clear concentration of urban parks in the periphery near the city centre, forming “green fingers” planned in the beginning of 20th century that extend along riverbeds and connect the city to Vitosha mountain in the south. Areas lacking pedestrian access to urban parks are overwhelmingly located north of the railway infrastructure, relatively close to the city centre. Moreover, significant clusters of residential buildings without access to urban parks are located in the southern periphery of the city around neighbourhoods developed in the last two decades without substantial plans for social, technical, or natural infrastructure. While these southern residential neighbourhoods are near the skirts of the mountains which represent a large-scale natural park, the homes north of the railway are much more disadvantaged being physically disconnected from the nearest green spaces.

Figure 12 - Parks and gardens according to the current General Spatial Plan (2008) and access to urban parks.

Source: Sofiaplan (<https://sofiaplan.bg/>)

Residential buildings with no pedestrian access to parks

These spatial analyses confirm a clear spatial division and lack of access to cultural and natural infrastructure for the residential neighbourhood north of the main railway line. The segregation caused primarily by railway infrastructure, riverbeds and the design of the urban

arteries is surely not the main reason behind the unequal income between the north and the south of Sofia. However, it could be argued that these infrastructural barriers exacerbate the lack of access to natural and cultural infrastructure experienced by disadvantaged residents' in the northern neighbourhoods to natural and cultural infrastructure.

Figure 13 - Mapping of infrastructural and spatial barriers around the main railway lines.

Hristo Botev neighbourhood as an apt case study

If we reduce the scale of our observations to the street level, one notices how Hristo Botev, one of the most spatially segregated neighbourhoods, suffers the consequences of the development of the railway infrastructure in Sofia (*Figure 13*). The neighbourhood is surrounded by three large infrastructural sites – the Poduyane Razpredelitelna (a temporarily abandoned railway yard and a still functioning train depot), the western side of Sofia Airport, and Slatinska concrete riverbed. All these large scale infrastructures enclose the Hristo Botev neighbourhood on all sides, leaving it with only three entrances: an underpass below the railways, a railway crossing (where tracks are temporarily removed but will soon be reinstalled) and a bridge over the river bed.

Hristo Botev residents report that from outside the neighbourhood has been perceived as housing a significant Roma population (Grekova et al., 2008: 128). This perception has led to racial stigmatisation, which has been reflected over time in neglected public infrastructure and minimal public investments – an issue common to similarly stigmatised areas. This lack of public investment was not addressed by the EU-financed projects in the Municipal Integrated Development Plan for the 2014-2020 EU budget period either. While there have been improvements in the latest budget period, the full plan has not yet been approved.

Figure 14 - The urban structure of the Hristo Botev neighbourhood and the barriers around it. The three entrances are marked with circles.

Hristo Botev neighbourhood – home to around 15,000 residents living mostly in townhouses and some apartment blocks – lacks any green spaces – neither urban parks, nor community gardens. Some residents have to cross the railway tracks through an underpass alongside the riverbed to the nearest park in Slatina (*Figure 14*). Families let their children play in the streets, resulting in a higher number of road accidents. In instances when the Slatinska River floods the underpass, residents resort to dangerous illegal crossings of the railway tracks. In one case some 15 years ago, the railway guards opened fire on a man crossing the railway tracks during one such flood.⁸

Long-time residents of Sofia that live outside the neighbourhood typically avoid Hristo Botev. The neighbourhood is served by only one bus line (No 79) that reaches the periphery of the city centre without crossing the neighbourhood. This results in travel times of over an hour

⁸ These witness observations have been kindly shared to us by a long-time resident and an activist of the Hristo Botev that has continuously fought a decade ago for improvement of public infrastructure in the neighbourhood.

to reach administrative services, cultural activities, and other parts of the city. Despite Sofia's compact urban structure, which is supposed to minimise long-distance inner city travel, Hristo Botev residents are bound to use cars for daily commuting.

Not all neighbourhoods from the north side of the railway line experience the same level of spatial segregation and isolation as Hristo Botev. Residential areas such as Orlandovtsi, Vasil Levski, Benkovski, which share similar characteristics – spacious boulevards, a rational street system, four-facade townhouses with gardens – have the potential for a high quality of life. They simply need better social and cultural infrastructure, better public, collective, and green spaces, and better connectivity with other parts of the city.

Figure 15 - The south entrance of the Hristo Botev neighbourhood – an underpass below the railway lines alongside the riverbed of the Slatinska river. (2016)

The Process As a Negotiation

Planning challenges of post-industrial urban renewal in Europe

The first part of this article demonstrated how Sofia's railway infrastructure of Sofia, similarly to that of many post-socialist cities, has been impacted by significant societal shifts. Previously taken-for-granted infrastructure systems can quickly decay or have deteriorated and investments have been withdrawn on a more or less permanent basis (Graham and Marvin, 2001). After the fall of state socialism, the Bulgarian state invested heavily in automotive highways and neglected railway infrastructure and transport. The decreasing significance of railways, combined with the relocation of industry from the inner city to Sofia's periphery, has left large, unused railway spaces that fragment the structure of the city.

The de-industrialisation process in Europe not only shifted economic paradigms, but also changed the management of urban spaces (Starczewski, 2023). While some cities, e.g. Duisburg, worked towards becoming “green cities” and emphasising green spaces, others, e.g. Essen and Berlin, adopted the “creative city” label (Florida, 2015) or the “entrepreneurial city” model (Hall & Hubbard 1998), e.g. Amsterdam, Manchester. While aiming for different functions restructuring, these approaches all strive to employ urban renewal strategies in addressing infrastructural decay.

Such large urban renewal projects present serious planning challenges. The complexity of land transformation projects, as reflected in their varying treatment in literature and by practitioners, makes post industrial redevelopment difficult to accomplish. (Loures, 2015). Topics such as contamination and liability need to be considered alongside real estate transactions, land use aspects, and community and economic development.

As Alice Mah states in her essay “Ruination and Post-industrial Urban Decline”

‘ Urban planners, developers, and municipalities have a limited repertoire of possible solutions to industrial decline. These models are based on assumptions that simply do not hold up in the majority of cases of old industrial cities: not all cities can be creative or competitive; not all urban development conditions are underpinned by conditions of economic growth (indeed many regeneration projects stalled or were abandoned following the 2008 recession); and physical regeneration alone cannot address the deepest problems of urban and industrial decline: stigmatization, toxic contamination, unemployment, poverty, and a lack of anything to replace the former industrial base’ (Mah, 2017, p. 208).

Still, many infrastructural areas are rapidly being developed as arenas for neoliberal planning (Tasan-Kok 2012). Often located near city centres or waterfronts and supported by existing infrastructure (Loures, 2015), these post-industrial landscapes represent one of the last remaining opportunities for land development in Western cities, where inner-city land is scarce. However, such profit-driven projects are faced with strong public criticism for exacerbating urban inequalities. Notable examples include ongoing protests against waterfront developments in Savamala District in Belgrade or Mediaspree in Berlin.

Infrastructural renewal planning in Sofia

Sofia faces similar challenges with its post-industrial landscapes, including pollution, complex land ownership and public opposition. After a period of uncontrolled post-socialist urban sprawl, which resulted in over-construction, loss of green spaces and monofunctional residential neighbourhoods, the city’s authorities have faced various protests against new

large-scale developments. However, the decay of lucrative railway sites in Sofia is not solely due to public outcry. These sites are owned by the National Company of Railway Infrastructure, a government organisation, similarly to most European cities. Effective infrastructural urban renewal of these areas requires multi-level institutional collaboration, such as in the case of the Port of Rotterdam where a cooperation between the municipality and the port authority facilitated redevelopment (Hill, 2018). In Bulgaria, however, political instability and general distrust among authorities in recent years have halted cooperation in inner city land restructuring, leaving railway areas in decay and dividing the city.

A sensitive approach to infrastructural regeneration

Despite these challenges, the delay in development has a positive aspect: it provides an opportunity to rethink and reboot existing planning strategies. The authors of this article, through their collective practice as part of Gradoscope⁹, took advantage of this situation and proposed a more inclusive and sensitive approach to railway area regeneration. Founded in 2021, the multidisciplinary collective emerged as a response to the shifting landscape of urbanism, offering a safe space to develop projects that are sensitive to the local communities and ecosystems. Rather than a classical planning office, Gradoscope positions itself in the long tradition of alternative planning practice to the classical procedural approach of modernism. Without embracing any specific planning tradition the practice aligns with advocacy planning (Davidoff, 1965), equity planning (Krumholz & Forester 1990), social planning (Greed, 1999) or insurgent planning (Sandercock, 1998).

⁹ Gradoscope (gradoscope.com) is a multidisciplinary collective founded in 2021 by Adriyana Mihaylova (communications expert), Ina Valkanova (architect) and Aneta Vasileva (architect). The practice grew with eight more people who joined the collective in the years to follow. The members are mostly with a professional background of architecture, communications, urban planning and graphic design. The collective works upon an adaptive methodology for sustainable multi-stakeholder dialogue that would develop shared visions for potential future projects of urban transformations. This includes creating platforms for discussions between governmental and academic institutions and the public.

Figure 16 - The riverbed of Slatinska river - the western border of the neighbourhood. (2016)

Gradoscope was tasked by the Municipality of Sofia to develop a strategy for the redevelopment of the areas between the Freight Station (Stochna gara) and Poduyane Razpredelitelna Station - the most central part of Sofia railway network that divides the city into a poorer northern and a wealthier southern part. Initially, discussions with the municipality revolved around a modern Keynesian approach of creating a structural mixed-use masterplan, very much in line with the municipality's planning practice. However, it quickly became clear that such a normative approach was not only reductionist given the complexity of the area but also impractical. The land in question was the property of the government, not the city, and at the time there was a political misalignment between the two institutions. The responsible governmental agency of National Railway Infrastructure Company had limited capacity for developing the land.

This situation presented an opportunity for Gradoscope to develop an approach based on social innovation (Moulaert, 2009) in contrast with positivist planning models (Healey, 2014). We started with an initial analysis of the sites and their potential for urban integration, looking at the broader spatial context, i.e. the areas from Stochna Gara to Poduyane Razpredelitelna Station. The initial idea was to organise a participatory workshop to discuss the results of the analysis with the experts of Sofia municipality. However, during fieldwork, the team discovered that Stochna Gara, built in 1914 as a freight logistical hub bearing all elements of tangible cultural heritage, was maintained and secured, but remained closed to the public and only used by the film industry. Recognising its potential, Gradoscope seized the opportunity to introduce the station to the citizens of Sofia, possibly as a venue for public debate on the area's renewal.

Figure 17 - Mapping of the urban structure, landscape elements and transport infrastructure - extract around the two abandoned railway stations *Stochna gara* and *Poduyane Razpreditelna station*

At that point, the University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy (UACEG) expressed interest in engaging with the redevelopment process. We established an academic collaboration between ETH Zürich, Università degli studi di Napoli, Politecnico di Milano, and UACEG. Within the framework of the international workshop, architecture and urbanism students from these four universities examined projects related to adaptive infrastructure in parallel, with each university focusing on their local context. Based on the analysis students proposed different future scenarios, including repurposing existing buildings for manufacturing, covered markets, shared offices, and cultural activation. Their project aimed to bridge the gap between the northern and southern communities by constructing pedestrian and bicycle bridges and a series of active public spaces (*Figure 19*).

What began as a workshop catering primarily to the municipality evolved into multidisciplinary roundtables with planners, administrators, activists, and investors, alongside an exhibition of student proposals. The idea to open up the building of *Stochna Gara* to the public, featuring such versatile activities, was initially rejected, because of NRIC's reluctance to relinquish control over the process, which would have constituted a departure from its mode of operation. However, after a complex negotiation process with NRIC, in June, 2021 the abandoned building of *Stochna Gara* opened its doors to the public not as a railway

station, but as a venue for interactive discussions, exhibition, and lectures on the future of the site.

Figure 18 - The main railway line - the south-eastern border of the neighbourhood (2016).

The event was successful in gaining the NRIC's trust, which began seeing Gradoscope as an independent partner and mediator between various institutions. Funded by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT), we staged a second round of roundtables involving more experts and activists. While the initial roundtables aimed to establish the area as a possible site of intervention with the goal of rejuvenating decaying infrastructure that can bridge the North-side divide of the city, the second round focused on refining concrete ideas, engaging stakeholders, and outlining possible future steps.

The round tables participants were grouped into four target categories: institutions, local residents, business and cultural actors, and experts and innovators. In the planning context of Sofia, those groups rarely meet, so our aim was to foster productive discussions between stakeholders with distinct interests. Most of the discussions were centred on the need for a collective vision, encompassing aspects such as security and safety, the development of active public spaces for play and recreation, cultural and economic revitalisation, reconnecting with the natural landscape, and a balance between profit-oriented spaces and social functions, tailored to the needs of the neighbourhood. The discussions proved that the more effective way to handle such a large area was not a normative top-down masterplan but rather tactical urbanism (Silva, 2016, Street Plan Collaborative) in selected areas that already harbour some activities. At the same time, these actions need to be part of a common framework to ensure they are not independent entities but contribute to a cohesive vision.

Figure 19 - Strategic ambiguity as a tool for overcoming inequality and deal with power dynamics

Gradoscope's approach was designed as an open-ended process from the outset, which means that it was not directed toward a certain product but adjusted to various strategic actions and multiple perspectives (Persyn, 2021). Throughout the process of community engagement, we collectively identified the next priorities. One of the first actions to be taken as a continuation of the project is establishing a common legal framework in which infrastructural spaces can become open to the public for tactical urban interventions. Owing to our open approach, the negotiation process has finally gained the trust of the NRIC, which is now willing to discuss potential partnerships with the Sofia municipality for the implementation of various social projects. This fragile coalition still requires strengthening through continuous engagement of activists, public actors, and different discussion formats.

The open-ended process, as a counter-initiative to normative planning, functions as a discursive arena where multiple voices and nuances shape a collective vision for rigid infrastructural spaces. It also allows a better understanding of the role of institutions, as well as professional and non-professional actors. Ultimately, the process highlights Gradoscope's positioning as a mediator between different stakeholders and interests, which grants them significant leverage, even though the collective is external to any institutional decision-making. Such a position of strategic ambiguity (Kaethler et al., 2017) is challenging, since it requires a clear reflection regarding our own values, intentions, and practices concerning the future of Stochna Gara. However, in the case of Sofia, this approach has proven to be a productive ground for creating a just urban transformation and dealing with inequalities.

Conclusions

The historical development of Sofia reveals that in the pre-industrial era, the plain's regional urban metabolism was almost fully circular. However, rapid urbanisation processes at the end of 19th and throughout the 20th century led to extensive industrial and extraction activities and concentrated around one third of the country's population in the capital. This growth brought about the deterioration of ecosystems and the extinction of a large part of the habitats and species in the valley. With industrialisation and the development of railways and the city's international transport connections, the urban metabolism shifted to a linear model, affecting the dependency on resources, and, most importantly, the quality of the living environment and the residents' health. Environmental degradation has disproportionately impacted poorer neighbourhoods and residents. Infrastructures began to divide the city on a poorer northern part and richer southern part. These differences are materialised as well on the street level – we observe poorer pedestrian access between north and south, less access to urban parks, natural environments, and cultural infrastructure for the northern neighbourhoods of the city. The case of Hristo Botev neighbourhood demonstrates extreme segregation of a residential zone from its urban environment and welfare infrastructure, as the area is enclosed by linear and spatial infrastructural barriers. While the construction of this infrastructure may not have been the result of a deliberate political decision to segregate the zone, the lack of action to improve urban connectivity leads to a deterioration of the quality of residents' daily life.

Gradoscope's activist mobilisation, as described in the paper, provides a platform for a dialogue between experts and citizens about the future urban development of the railway corridor. The initiative involving multiple actors could be a legitimate way to formulate a shared vision for overcoming the environmental and social challenges that had accumulated due to the continuous industrialisation of the Sofia plain.

The students' projects (*Figure 20*), created during the academic exchange for the area of the abandoned freight station (Stochna Gara) reveal speculative, yet feasible proposals for adaptive infrastructures to bridge the divide between technical and social urban facilities. These proposals, illustrated by playful imagery, can foster and strengthen a shared understanding about possible futures of these sites. These students' proposals align with a conception of infrastructure projects as intersections of technology, public space, landscape, and social facilities. Kelly Shannon and Marcel Smets collect a large palette of urban infrastructure projects (2010) that showcase the changing perceptions about spatial patterns of mobility and technology in contemporary territorial development. Many of the projects reflect processes of privatisation of public spaces following the oil crises of the 1970s. Nevertheless, they are all good examples of the possibilities in blurring boundaries between

the disciplines of landscape planning, urbanism, architecture, design, and other social sciences. Infrastructure project creation can also address climate adaptation (Hill, 2012), landscape design harmonious with the forces and qualities of nature (McHarg, 1969), and processes of experimentation and negotiation in order to ensure spatial quality (Segers et al., 2016).

Figure 20 - Students projects for the freight station area (Stochna gara). Authors: Maria Petkova, Todor Todorov, Teodosi Stavrev, Kamen Nikov

The facilitation of open-ended negotiation processes can foster innovative collaboration between institutions, citizens, and private actors, while taking into account the needs of weaker stakeholders that would be affected by further development. This approach could result in projects that prioritise social and natural infrastructures over profit, thus improving surrounding neighbourhoods and inscribing these actions into a broader collectively created shared vision for spatial and climate justice.

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